

Delhi: *Pages from a Forgotten History* by Arthur Dudley (Hay House India, New Delhi, 2015, ISBN: 938139878X / 978-9381398784)

Errata and Works Cited, updated 3 January 2016 (version 3)

ERRATA AND CLARIFICATIONS

[I am grateful to the readers who pointed out some of these errors. –AD]

On pg 78 for “*Nihāyat al-Jamāl* (The Peak of Beauty, 1325)” read “*Nihāyat al-Kamāl* (The Peak of Perfection, 1325)” —although Sharma 2005 cites the title as the former, other scholars and the published edition (Qaisariyah Press, Delhi, 1913-4) give the latter.

On pg 87 the fn on *hadīs* is misleading. Instead read “The *hadīs* are the reported sayings and actions of the Prophet that provide guidance for Muslims. Whereas the Qur’ān is considered by Muslims as a complete and immutable divine text, there has always been a vibrant tradition of assessing how trustworthy a particular *hadīs* is.”

On pg 92 for “the four schools” read “the four Sunni schools”.

On pg 117 the paragraph beginning “In this state...” is a direct quotation and should be formatted as a blockquote.

On pg 130 for “He was intolerant...” read “He was austere...”. Given the valence that the label “intolerant” has taken on in Indian politics in 2015, I hesitate to use it so cavalierly in a thumbnail sketch of a controversial historical figure like Aurangzeb.

On pg 147, a note on the *Zafarnāmah*: The poem is included in the Sikh religious text *Dasam Granth* along with other works in various languages attributed to the Tenth Sikh Guru, Gobind Singh. The *Dasam Granth* includes about a thousand verses in Persian.

On pg 161, a note on the paragraph beginning “In the second half...”: Police vocabulary is another context where Persian words common in Urdu have been retained in some parts of India up to the present. According to the *Hindustan Times*, police officers in Delhi are taught 132 such words in training and routinely use them. A public interest litigation (PIL) was filed in the high court to have these replaced with Hindi or English equivalents, but the police oppose this, arguing (to my mind rightly so) that the official Hindi

equivalents would be more confusing than the terms used now (Soibam Rocky Singh, “Delhi cops prefer using Urdu words in FIRs and daily documentation”, 26 Oct. 2015, <http://www.hindustantimes.com/delhi/delhi-cops-prefer-using-urdu-words-in-firs-and-daily-documentation/story-6noLfjjV7wIOR4j4vzlluK.html>).

On pg 165 for “out of Bay of Bengal” read “out of the Bay of Bengal”.

On pg 168 for “Man’s bravery and God’s grace” read “Men’s bravery and God’s grace”.

On pg 176 in fn for “There were also called...” read “They were also called...”.

On pg 178, a note on the paragraph beginning “Even after 1835...”: A typical mid-nineteenth-century British view on Persian is expressed by a judge in an 1852 report on the Calcutta Madrasah: “What is it to us whether the rising generation of Mussalmans know Persian or not? or why should we trouble ourselves about a language which we have sedulously excluded from our courts and offices, and which if we let it alone, will soon in India die a natural death” (qtd Rahman 1999: 56). The British assumed that over time English would naturally fill the roles formerly held by Persian.

On pg 179, a note on the last paragraph: Expressing the British fear that well-educated Indians represented a challenge to the colonial project, the Viceroy Lord Lytton wrote in 1877 that “the only political representatives of native opinion are the Babus, whom we have educated to write semi-seditious articles in the native Press, and who really represent nothing but the social anomaly of their own position” (qtd. Judd 2004:103). Apparently in response to the same concern, Cambridge University introduced a quota system in 1909 to limit the number of Indian students studying at the university (Zachariah 2004: 23-4)

On pg 196 for “Melting into same-tonguednesses with Nazīrī and Ṣā’ib” read “Melting into same-tonguednesses with Zuhūrī and Ṣā’ib”.

On pg 201 for “all the changes they wrought” read “all the changes they had wrought”.

On pg 272 for “‘āqil NA-SHAWAD HAR ĀNKIH” read “‘ĀQIL NA-SHAWAD HAR ĀNKIH”.

Rahman 1999 added to works cited.

On the front book jacket flap in the second paragraph for “from Turkey to eastern China” read “from Turkey to western China”.

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